

MULTI-STAGE PATCH DIFFUSION AND CONTRASTIVE-SDE

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Abstract

In this work, we address two key problems in diffusion models: (1) Efficiency of diffusion models, and (2) unpaired image-to-image (I2I) translation. Score-based diffusion models have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in generative tasks. Their ability to approximate complex data distributions through stochastic differential equations (SDEs) enables them to generate high-fidelity and diverse outputs, making them particularly effective for unconditional image generation and unpaired I2I translation. To enhance efficiency, we propose an integrated approach that combines Patch Diffusion with a Multi-Stage Framework to enhance both training efficiency and generative quality. Patch Diffusion introduces a patch-wise training methodology that employs randomized patch sizes and conditional score functions with location-based coordinate channels, enabling faster convergence and improved performance on smaller datasets. The Multi-Stage Framework, on the other hand, optimizes parameter utilization across different diffusion timesteps by segmenting them into distinct intervals, employing tailored multi-decoder U-Net architectures, and addressing inefficiencies such as gradient dissimilarity. For unpaired I2I translation, we propose a time-based contrastive learning method, Contrastive SDE, where a model is trained using SimCLR by treating an image and its domain-invariant representation as a positive pair. This helps the model retain features consistent across domains while suppressing those specific to individual domains. The trained contrastive model is then used to guide the inference process of a pretrained SDE for image-to-image translation. Experimental results demonstrate a substantial reduction in training time, although the FID scores remain suboptimal across datasets such as CIFAR10 and CelebA, highlighting both the promise and current limitations of the proposed framework in democratizing diffusion model training for broader applications. We further conduct empirical comparisons of Contrastive SDE with several baselines across three standard unpaired I2I tasks, evaluated using four common metrics. Contrastive SDE achieves performance comparable to state-of-the-art methods on several metrics. Moreover, our model converges significantly faster and requires neither label supervision nor classifier training, making it a more efficient alternative for unpaired image-to-image translation.

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1 Introduction

Diffusion models have gained prominence for their generative capabilities across a wide range of applications which includes unconditional image generation, image inpainting, super-resolution, text-to-image, and video generation. Despite their impressive generative abilities, diffusion models face challenges with slow training and sampling, limiting their use in applications that require real-time generation. These challenges mainly arise from the need of iterative forward and reverse diffusion processes with a large model of many parameters to train and infer over multiple timesteps. Addressing this challenge, one of the approaches introduced by [27] A Multi-Stage Framework comprising two components: (1) a U-net architecture with multiple decoders, and (2) a novel algorithm for partitioning timesteps into separate stages through clustering.

Complementing this, Patch Diffusion [26], a general patch-based training framework, substantially reduces training time while enhancing data efficiency. This method achieves faster training, enhanced data efficiency, and robust performance on smaller datasets. By integrating both approaches, we propose a unified training approach that combines patch-wise conditioning with multi-stage optimization. This unified framework offers a promising solution for accessible, efficient, and scalable diffusion model training.

While training a diffusion model is generally more computationally intensive than inference, our focus is on a task that can be addressed using inference alone that is unpaired image-to-image translation. In this setting, there is no direct correspondence between samples from the source and target domains. To solve this problem, we rely solely on a pretrained diffusion model trained on the target domain. The objective is to guide the inference process of this model to translate an image from the source domain into the target domain, while retaining the essential characteristics of the source. These characteristics, referred to as domain-invariant features, include aspects such as color and texture. Meanwhile, features specific to the source domain—such as pose or identity—should be removed. Formally, a successful translation preserves domain-invariant features while discarding domain-specific ones.

Early approaches to unpaired image-to-image translation relied on GAN-based methods [7, 16]. However, these models often face issues such as mode collapse, unstable training, and limited diversity in generated outputs. In recent years, score-based diffusion models (SBDMs) [17] have emerged as state-of-the-art for generating high-quality, diverse images. Existing diffusion models often use classifier guidance to ensure that generated images retain domain-invariant features—such as color and texture—while discarding domain-specific features like identity, pose, or shape. More recent strategies introduce energy-based guidance [23] to guide generation toward semantically meaningful outputs.

We take a different perspective by framing this challenge as a contrastive learning problem—where the goal is to pull domain-invariant features closer in the representation space while pushing domain-specific features apart. Motivated by this perspective, we propose a time-dependent contrastive model that learns to retain domain-invariant features and discard domain-specific ones at various diffusion time steps. This model is then used to guide the inference of a pretrained diffusion model, leading to translations that match the target domain while ignoring

irrelevant source-specific traits.

To evaluate both the guidance strategy and training efficiency, we conduct experiments across two settings. First, we assess our contrastive guidance model for unpaired image-to-image translation on standard datasets such as AFHQ [13] and CelebA [9], covering tasks like Cat \rightarrow Dog, Wild \rightarrow Dog, and Male \rightarrow Female. Our method performs competitively with state-of-the-art approaches across multiple evaluation metrics, while offering a simpler and more targeted alternative to classifier-based guidance. Second, to validate the training efficiency of our unified framework, we evaluate the multi-stage patch diffusion approach on CIFAR-10 and CelebA for unconditional image generation. The results demonstrate improved training speed and data efficiency but, quality of generated image was compromised.

2 Literature Review

As generative models, diffusion-based approaches have shown remarkable effectiveness, excelling in tasks such as image synthesis, video generation, and text-to-image translation. Building on their foundational principles, numerous methods have been proposed to address the challenges of training efficiency and scalability.

One direction focuses on optimizing the training process. Techniques such as DDIM [20], TDPM [24], and EDM [21]-Sampling have reduced inference times but have limited impact on overall training efficiency. Meanwhile, hierarchical approaches like Cascaded Diffusion stabilize training by adopting multi-resolution designs, though these methods often require significant computational resources. The Multi-Stage Framework [27] takes this further by segmenting timesteps into manageable intervals, leveraging shared encoder architectures with interval-specific decoders to reduce parameter redundancy and enhance gradient consistency. This method has demonstrated significant improvements in training efficiency and scalability across large-scale datasets.

A complementary area of exploration addresses data efficiency and computational bottlenecks through patch-based strategies. The Patch Diffusion [26] framework introduces a patch-wise training methodology, incorporating randomized patch sizes and location-based conditioning. These innovations allow the model to learn cross-region dependencies while dramatically reducing computational costs. Patch Diffusion achieves remarkable results on smaller datasets, significantly lowering the barrier to entry for researchers and practitioners with limited resources.

By merging these ideas, a unified methodology integrating Patch Diffusion into the Multi-Stage Framework provides an opportunity to leverage the strengths of both approaches. While the Multi-Stage Framework ensures efficient parameter utilization and resource allocation, Patch Diffusion adds a scalable patch-based conditioning mechanism that enhances both training speed and generative quality. Together, these advancements promise to push the boundaries of diffusion model accessibility, scalability, and efficiency, making them more practical for diverse applications.

As diffusion models are computationally expensive to train, one of the tasks that does not require training a diffusion model from scratch is guiding a diffusion model inference for an image-to-

image translation. Unpaired I2I translation became widely adopted with methods like CycleGAN [7], which introduced cycle-consistency to learn mappings without paired data. Although GAN-based techniques such as MUNIT [8] and DRIT [10] enhanced diversity and style transfer, they tended to be unstable and lack expressiveness. In recent times, diffusion models such as Palette [22] and Score-Decomposed Diffusion Models (SDDM) [25] have established state-of-the-art(SOTA) performance on unpaired I2I tasks with improved fidelity and diversity. However, most of these methods lack direct control over domain-invariant features to be retained and may, in some cases, transfer unwanted domain-specific artifacts. EGSDE [23] introduced energy-guided stochastic differential equations, employing an energy function trained on both source and target domains to guide the inference process of a pretrained SDE. Similarly, SDEdit [19] provided a framework for image editing by partially denoising and then re-synthesizing images, while ILVR [18] enabled precise control by conditioning on low-frequency content during the diffusion process. SDEdit and ILVR, though powerful, primarily focus on editing or conditional synthesis rather than learning domain-invariant features for unpaired translation. Methods like SDEdit and EGSDE have attempted to bridge gaps by refining the generative process but still fall short in achieving deliberate domain-invariant feature retention.

Concurrently, contrastive learning has emerged as a building block for representation learning, and SimCLR [11] showed that data augmentation and a contrastive loss can provide robust and generalizable visual features. Supervised contrastive learning [15] further used label information to improve feature quality, with applications to multiple downstream tasks. However, most contrastive learning research has focused on representation learning rather than generative modeling, with limited work on its application to image translation or diffusion processes for removing domain-specific bias.

Recently, studies have begun exploring the integration of contrastive learning with diffusion models to improve domain-invariant feature preservation and translation quality [28]. While their approach incorporates contrastive loss within a latent diffusion model to guide image-to-image translation, it does not explicitly integrate time-dependent contrastive learning into the diffusion process. Herein lies the gap for techniques that employ time-dependent contrastive approaches to supervise diffusion models to preserve more domain-invariant features and enhance unpaired I2I translation quality.

3 Preliminary

3.1 Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models

Target samples are produced by Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs) [14] by repeatedly employing a denoising network to remove noise from a conventional Gaussian variable. By incorporating random noise into actual data and teaching it to anticipate the noise, this network is trained. Gaussian noise is progressively added by a Markov chain method, beginning with the original data y^0 :

$$p(y^{1:N}|y^0) = \prod_{i=1}^N p(y^i|y^{i-1}) \quad (1)$$

where N indicates the highest number of diffusion steps. The steps that add noise are as follows:

$$p(y^i|y^{i-1}) := \mathcal{N}\left(y^i; \sqrt{1 - \gamma_i}y^{i-1}, \gamma_i I\right) \quad (2)$$

The entire process in which noise is added is called the forward process and this process doesn't involve any neural network, so no training is done in this phase. Hyperparameters involved in this phase are $\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_N \in (0, 1)$. This process can then be fastened by precomputing parameters $\beta_i = 1 - \gamma_i$ and $\bar{\beta}_i = \prod_{r=0}^i \beta_r$. By using the reparameterization trick to extract the corrupted sample at level i in closed form is as follows:

$$y^i = \sqrt{\bar{\beta}_i}y^0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\beta}_i}\alpha \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is the standard gaussian distribution. Additionally, the reverse process is defined as a Markov chain:

$$q_\phi(y^{0:N}) := q(y^N) \prod_{i=N}^1 q_\phi(y^{i-1}|y^i) \quad (4)$$

The probability of denoising step is a Gaussian distribution with mean ϵ_ϕ and variance σ_ϕ is

$$q_\phi(y^{i-1}|y^i) = \mathcal{N}(y^{i-1}; \epsilon_\phi(y^i, i), \sigma_\phi(y^i, i)) \quad (5)$$

The Gaussian noise added at that particular step i is removed by using this denoising network. DDPMs also learn to maximize the Evidence Lower Bound(ELBO) similar to VAEs:

$$\text{ELBO}(\phi) = \mathbb{E}p(y^{0:N}) [\log q_\phi(y^{0:N}) - \log p(y^{1:N}|y^0)] \quad (6)$$

But writing this ELBO in the form of code can become computationally intensive due to too many denoising steps. So in the training we calculate the loss by uniformly sampling i from 1 to N :

$$\mathcal{L}_i(\phi) = \mathbb{D}_{KL}(p(y^{i-1}|y^i, y^0) || q_\phi(y^{i-1}|y^i)) \quad (7)$$

The posterior probability of diffusion variable at $i - 1$ th step given i th and unnoised version is

$$p(y^{i-1}|y^i, y^0) = \mathcal{N}\left(y^{i-1}; \tilde{\epsilon}(y^i, y^0, i), \tilde{\delta}_i I\right) \quad (8)$$

where

$$\tilde{\epsilon}(y^i, y^0, i) = \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\beta}_i - 1}\gamma_i}{1 - \bar{\beta}_i - 1}y^0 + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\beta}_i}(1 - \bar{\beta}_{i-1})}{1 - \bar{\beta}_i}y^i$$

$$\tilde{\gamma}_i = \frac{1 - \bar{\beta}_i - 1}{1 - \bar{\beta}_i} \gamma_i$$

The loss function is simplified to speed up the training of DDPMs :

$$\mathcal{L}^{i\text{new}}(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{y^0, i, \mu} \left[\left\| \mu - \mu_\phi(\sqrt{\bar{\beta}_i} y_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\beta}_i} \mu) \right\|^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

And the neural network $\mu_\phi(\cdot)$ is employed to forecast the reparameterization noise μ . In every training iteration, we compute gradients on $\nabla_\phi \mathcal{L}^{i\text{new}}(\phi)$ after drawing $i \sim \text{Uniform}(1, \dots, N)$ and $\mu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Using the noise prediction network $\mu_\phi(\cdot)$, we may sample the data at the $(i - 1)^{\text{th}}$ step given y^i in order to reconstruct the data:

$$y^{i-1} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta_n}} \left(y_i - \frac{1 - \beta_i}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\beta}_i}} \mu_\phi(y_i, i) \right), \frac{1 - \bar{\beta}_{i-1}}{1 - \bar{\beta}_i} \gamma_i I \right) \quad (10)$$

Refer [14] for understanding more about DDPMs.

3.2 Score Based Diffusion Models

Unlike vanilla DDPMs, which uses a discrete Markov chain for the forward and reverse processes, Score-Based Diffusion Models (SBDMs) [17] adopt a continuous-time formulation based on stochastic differential equations (SDEs). In SBDMs, the forward process perturbs the data using an SDE of the form

$$dy^t = f(t)y^t dt + g(t) d\omega_t \quad (11)$$

The reverse process aims to recover $p(x)$ by denoising step-by-step, guided by the reverse SDE:

$$dy^t = [f(y^t, t) - g^2(t) \nabla_y \log p_{\sigma_t}(y^t)] dt + g(t) dw \quad (12)$$

where $f(y, t)$ is the drift coefficient, $g(t)$ is the diffusion coefficient, $\nabla_y \log p_{\sigma_t}(y)$ is the score function, and dw is the noise term. For deterministic modeling, the reverse SDE can be transformed into the probability flow ODE:

$$dy^t = [f(y^t, t) - 0.5g^2(t) \nabla_y \log p_{\sigma_t}(y^t)] dt \quad (13)$$

The training objective minimizes the denoising score-matching loss to learn this score function:

$$L = \mathbb{E}_{t, y^t} \left\| s_\theta(y^t, t) - \nabla_{y^t} \log p_t(y^t) \right\|^2 \quad (14)$$

This continuous formulation allows SBDMs to use advanced numerical solvers for the reverse process, reduces sampling steps considerably compared to DDPM, yet maintains high-quality outputs.

3.3 Contrastive Learning

Contrastive learning aims to learn a representation function $f_\theta(\cdot)$ by bringing similar (positive) samples closer and pushing dissimilar (negative) ones apart in the embedding space. Formally, given two views x_i and x_j the contrastive loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{contrast}} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(f_\theta(x_i), f_\theta(x_j))/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(f_\theta(x_i), f_\theta(x_k))/\tau)} \quad (15)$$

where $\text{sim}(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes cosine similarity and τ is a temperature hyperparameter.

3.3.1 Unsupervised Contrastive Loss

SimCLR [11] introduces the NT-Xent loss (Normalized Temperature-scaled Cross Entropy Loss), operates on positive pairs $(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{x}_j)$ of augmented views derived from the same data point. It aims to maximize the similarity between the representations (z_i, z_j) , $z = f_\theta(x)$ where z is the projection of the encoder output. and considers all other pairs as negatives. The loss is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-Xent}} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_k)/\tau)} \quad (16)$$

3.3.2 Semi-Supervised Contrastive Learning

SimCLR v2 [12] and FixMatch+Contrastive [15] extend contrastive learning with limited labeled data. The loss becomes a hybrid:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{NT-Xent}} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{sup}} \quad (17)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{sup} is the supervised loss (e.g., cross-entropy), and λ balances the two. These methods are used when only a small portion of data is labeled, allowing the model to benefit from both labeled supervision and unlabeled contrastive structure.

3.3.3 Supervised Contrastive Loss

SupCon [15] modifies the contrastive loss to build upon label information by using all positives in the batch with the same label:

$$L_{\text{sup}} = -\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{|P(i)|} \sum_{p \in P(i)} \log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_p)/\tau)}{\sum_{a \in A(i)} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_a)/\tau)} \quad (18)$$

where $P(i)$ and $A(i)$ denote positive and all other samples for the anchor i . SupCon is effective in fully supervised settings like fine-grained classification, where class boundaries are subtle and the model must learn differences within the same class. Given the absence of labeled data for domain-invariant and domain-specific features, we address this problem in an unsupervised setting using the NT-Xent loss.

4 Multi-Stage-Patch Approach

Figure 1: Unified and Multistage Architectures.(Source [4])

4.1 Multi-Stage Framework

Traditional diffusion model architectures, such as those in DDPM and Score SDE, treat all timesteps uniformly, using the same model for the entire range of noise levels. However, recent research has highlighted potential gains from addressing the differences between noise levels. Inefficiencies arise due to:

- **Overparameterization and Underfitting:** Unified architectures often allocate the same amount of parameters to all intervals, regardless of their specific requirements. For example, high-noise intervals demand fewer parameters, whereas low-noise intervals benefit from greater model capacity. Using a single model for all intervals leads to underutilization in some intervals (underfitting) and unnecessary redundancy in others (overparameterization).
- **Gradient Dissimilarity:** Gradient profiles vary significantly across different noise levels. Unified architectures compute gradients across all timesteps in a single batch, which can lead to inefficient updates. In contrast, treating each interval separately better aligns gradient updates with the specific requirements of each timestep, improving training efficiency.

To tackle these, we first propose a multi-stage U-Net architecture design, followed by a novel clustering approach for selecting optimal intervals to partition the full timestep range $[0, 1]$.

4.1.1 Multi-stage U-Net Architectures

We divide the full timestep range $[0, 1]$ into multiple segments, such as three intervals. $[0, t_1)$, $[t_1, t_2)$, and $[t_2, 1]$. For the architecture, we propose the following:

Single shared encoder is used across all timestep intervals: for each interval, we employ a common encoder architecture, analogous to the one in the original U-Net design. [7]. This prevents overfitting and maintains semantic consistency in the latent space (h-space) across all timesteps. Separate decoders for different time intervals: Decoders are tailored for specific intervals, optimizing parameter allocation based on the unique requirements of each timestep. For intervals with high noise (closer to random noise), simpler decoders are sufficient, while intervals with low noise (closer to the data) require more complex decoders.

4.1.2 Optimal Denoiser based TimeStep Clustering

Consider training a diffusion model denoiser function $\mu_\phi(y, t)$ parameterized by ϕ using a dataset $\{x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n\}_{i=1}^N$ by

$$\min_{\phi} \mathcal{L}(\mu_\phi; t) = \mathbb{E}_{y^0, y^t, \mu} [\|\mu - \mu_\phi(y^t, t)\|^2] \quad (19)$$

where $y^0 \sim p_{\text{data}}(y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(y - x_i)$, $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$, and $y^t \sim p_t(y^t | y^0) = \mathcal{N}(y^t; s_t y^0, s_t^2 \sigma_t^2 I)$ with perturbation parameters s_t and σ_t . The parameters s_t and σ_t are designed such that: (i) the data distribution is approximately estimated when $t = 0$, and (ii) a nearly standard Gaussian distribution is obtained when $t = 1$. Then, the optimal denoiser at t , defined as

$$\mu_\phi^*(y; t) = \arg \min_{\mu_\phi} \mathcal{L}(\mu_\phi; t) \quad (20)$$

, is given by

$$\mu_\phi^*(y; t) = \frac{1}{s_t \sigma_t} \left[y - s_t \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{N}(y; s_t x_i, s_t^2 \sigma_t^2 I) x_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{N}(y; s_t x_i, s_t^2 \sigma_t^2 I)} \right]. \quad (21)$$

The function distance of the optimal denoiser at any given timestep t_a, t_b is defined as:

$$\mathcal{D}(\mu_{t_a}^*, \mu_{t_b}^*, y_0, \mu) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{1}(|\mu_{t_a}^*(y_{t_a}) - \mu_{t_b}^*(y_{t_b})|_i \leq \eta) \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ denotes the indicator function, η represents a pre-defined threshold, $y_{t_b} = s_{t_b} y_0 + s_{t_b} \sigma_{t_b} \mu$, and $y_{t_a} = s_{t_a} y_0 + s_{t_a} \sigma_{t_a} \mu$. Accordingly, we define the functional similarity between the optimal denoisers at timesteps t_a and t_b as:

$$\mathcal{S}(\mu_{t_a}^*, \mu_{t_b}^*) = \mathbb{E}_{y_0 \sim p_{\text{data}}} \mathbb{E}_{\mu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)} [\mathcal{D}(\mu_{t_a}^*, \mu_{t_b}^*, y_0, \mu)]. \quad (23)$$

Based on the design, we formulate the following optimization problem to identify the largest t_1 and the smallest t_2 as:

$$t_1 \leftarrow \arg \max_{\tau} \{ \mathbb{E}_{t \sim [0, \tau]} [\mathcal{S}(\mu_t^*, \mu_0^*)] \geq \alpha \},$$

$$t_2 \leftarrow \arg \min_{\tau} \{ \mathbb{E}_{t \sim [\tau, 1]} [\mathcal{S}(\mu_t^*, \mu_1^*)] \geq \alpha \}.$$

Algorithm 1 Optimal Denoiser-Guided Timestep Clustering

1: **Input:** Total samples K , optimal denoiser function $\mu_{\phi}^*(x, t)$, thresholds α, η , dataset p_{data}
2: **Initialize:** $\mathcal{S}_0 = \mathcal{S}_1 = \emptyset$
3: **Output:** Timesteps t_1, t_2
4: **for** $k = 1$ to K **do**
5: Sample $y_k \sim p_{\text{data}}, \epsilon_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), t_k \sim [0, 1]$
6: $S_k^0 \leftarrow \mathcal{D}(\epsilon_{t_k}, \epsilon_0, y_k, \epsilon_k)$
7: $S_k^1 \leftarrow \mathcal{D}(\epsilon_{t_k}, \epsilon_1, y_k, \epsilon_k)$
8: $\mathcal{S}_0 \leftarrow \mathcal{S}_0 \cup \{(t_k, S_k^0)\}$
9: $\mathcal{S}_1 \leftarrow \mathcal{S}_1 \cup \{(t_k, S_k^1)\}$
10: **end for**
11: $t_1 = \arg \max_{\tau} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{(t_k, S_k^0) \in \mathcal{S}_0} S_k^0 \cdot \mathbf{1}(t_k \leq \tau)}{\sum_{(t_k, S_k^0) \in \mathcal{S}_0} \mathbf{1}(t_k \leq \tau)} \geq \alpha \right\}$
12: $t_2 = \arg \min_{\tau} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{(t_k, S_k^1) \in \mathcal{S}_1} S_k^1 \cdot \mathbf{1}(t_k \geq \tau)}{\sum_{(t_k, S_k^1) \in \mathcal{S}_1} \mathbf{1}(t_k \geq \tau)} \geq \eta \right\}$

4.2 Patch Diffusion

4.2.1 Patch-Wise Score Matching

We build a denoiser, $D_{\theta}(x; \sigma_t)$. For every patch that is divided, we use score-matching just like the score function in SBDM. The goal of the proposed method is to minimize the expected L2 denoising error for samples drawn from the data distribution $p(y)$, independently for each σ_t :

$$\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p(y)} \mathbb{E}_{\mu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_t^2 I)} \|D_{\theta}(y + \mu; \sigma_t) - x\|_2^2 \quad (24)$$

Thus, we define the score function as:

$$s_{\theta}(y, \sigma_t) = \frac{D_{\theta}(y; \sigma_t) - y}{\sigma_t^2}. \quad (25)$$

Rather than applying score matching to entire images, we propose learning the score function on patches of random sizes. For any $y \sim p(y)$, We begin by randomly cropping small patches $y_{i,j,s}$, where (i, j) denotes the top-left corner pixel coordinates of the patch, and s represents the patch size (e.g., $s = 32$). Denoising score matching is then performed on these patches, conditioned on their corresponding sizes and locations, and can be formulated as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p(y), \mu \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_t^2 I), (i,j,s) \sim \mathcal{U}} \|D_{\theta}(\tilde{y}_{i,j,s}; \sigma_t, i, j, s) - y_{i,j,s}\|_2^2 \quad (26)$$

where $\tilde{y}_{i,j,s} = y_{i,j,s} + \mu$, and \mathcal{U} denotes the uniform distribution over the corresponding value ranges (e.g., $i \sim [-1, 1]$). Consequently, our conditional score function $s_{\theta}(y, \sigma_t, i, j, s)$ is

defined over each local patch, with the scores being learned by conditioning on the patch’s location and size.

Training with Equation (26) significantly accelerates convergence, as it operates on small local patches. However, a key challenge arises from the fact that the score function $s_\theta(y, \sigma_t, i, j, s)$ observes local regions and may fail to capture global, cross-patch dependencies. In other words, the scores predicted from neighboring patches must collectively form a coherent score field to enable consistent image reconstruction during sampling.

To overcome this limitation, we introduce two strategies: 1. Random Patch Sizes: Patch sizes are sampled from both small and large patches. Larger patches can be interpreted as compositions of smaller ones, encouraging s_θ to learn how to integrate scores across local regions into a unified and coherent score map when trained with larger patches. 2. Incorporating Full-Size Images: To ensure that the reverse diffusion process reliably converges to the original data distribution, a small proportion of full-resolution images is included during training.

4.2.2 Progressive and Stochastic Patch Size Scheduling

We introduce a patch-size scheduling strategy. Let l represent the proportion of training iterations that use full-resolution images as input, and let R denote the original resolution of image. The available patch size options are defined as:

$$s \sim l_s := \begin{cases} R & \text{when } s = R, \\ \frac{3}{5}(1 - l) & \text{when } s = \frac{R}{2}, \\ \frac{2}{5}(1 - l) & \text{when } s = \frac{R}{4}. \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

We consider two approaches for patch-size scheduling: 1. Stochastic: In this method, for each mini-batch during training, we randomly sample the patch size $s \sim l_s$ where the probability mass function is defined in Equation (27). 2. Progressive: Here, we gradually increase the patch size throughout training. For the first $\frac{2}{5}(1 - l)$ portion of the training iterations, we fix the patch size to $s = \frac{R}{4}$. In the next $\frac{3}{5}(1 - l)$ iterations, we increase the patch size to $s = \frac{R}{2}$. Finally, full-size images are used for the remaining l fraction of the total training iterations

Empirically, we observe setting $l = 0.5$ with stochastic scheduling strikes a good balance between training speed and generation quality. Regarding the denoiser D_θ handle image patches of varying sizes. This is made possible by the fully convolutional nature of the U-Net architecture [5]. Since convolutional layers can adapt to different input resolutions by sliding their filters across the spatial dimensions, our patch-based training approach seamlessly integrates with any U-Net-based diffusion model. This architectural flexibility also contributes to faster and more efficient sampling.

4.2.3 Conditional Coordinates for Patch Location

To simplify how patch locations are incorporated, we introduce a pixel-level coordinate system. Specifically, we normalize pixel coordinates to the range $[-1, 1]$ based on the original image

resolution, where the top-left corner is set to $(-1, -1)$ and the bottom right corner as $(1, 1)$.

For any image patch $x_{i,j,s}$, we extract its pixel coordinates i and j and encode them as two additional channels. During training, each sample in a batch is independently and randomly cropped using a sampled patch size, and the corresponding coordinate channels are computed. These two coordinate channels are then concatenated with the original image channels to serve as input to the denoiser D_θ .

When evaluating the loss specified in Equation (27), we exclude the reconstructed coordinate channels and focus solely on minimizing the loss for the image channel. The combination of the pixel-level coordinate system and random patch sizes can be interpreted as a form of data augmentation. For instance, given an image of resolution 128×128 , and patch size $s = 32$, there are $(128 - 32 + 1)^2 = 9409$ possible distinct patch locations. This diversity in patch selection effectively increases the variety of training samples. Therefore, we argue that training diffusion models on patch-wise data enhances their data efficiency. By using patch training approach for Multi stage architecture can significantly improve the training efficiency of the model. Experiments are conducted on both the approaches

5 Contrastive-SDE

For unpaired image to image translation, we introduce a time-dependent contrastive learning method where a neural network F is trained to focus on domain-invariant features while suppressing domain-specific ones using the contrastive NT-Xent loss. This network is later used to guide the inference of a pretrained SDE via a guidance function \mathcal{Q} .

5.1 Contrastive Model Training

The core idea is to treat the image and its domain-invariant feature as a positive pair, while considering the image and its domain-specific feature as a negative pair. However, the NT-Xent loss treats all samples except the positive as negatives, which introduces a challenge in our setup. To address this, we ensure that domain-specific features are implicitly ignored during training. A theoretical explanation for this behavior is provided in the appendix.

We begin by training a U-Net-based model F , where each input is conditioned on the diffusion timestep through a learned time embedding. As shown in Figure 2, this architecture consists of a U-Net with residual and attention blocks operating at multiple scales. For each image x and its low-pass filtered version \bar{x} , the model extracts hidden representations h_i and h_j . A projection head then transforms these into contrastive features z_i and z_j , which are used to compute the NT-Xent loss as follows:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{k=1}^N [\ell(2k - 1, 2k) + \ell(2k, 2k - 1)] \quad (28)$$

 Figure 2: Architecture of the contrastive model F

$$\ell_{i,j} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k=1}^{2N} \mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_k)/\tau)} \quad (29)$$

Here, $\text{sim}(u, v) = \frac{u^T v}{|u||v|}$ is the cosine similarity between vectors u and v , and τ is a temperature parameter. The indicator function $\mathbb{1}_{[k \neq i]}$ is 1 when $k \neq i$ and 0 otherwise. This contrastive setup is simpler to train compared to building a classifier from scratch for guidance purpose.

5.2 Guiding Diffusion

Contrastive-SDE models the conditional distribution $p(y_0|x_0)$ by combining a pretrained SDE with a guidance function $\mathcal{Q}(y, x, t)$ derived from the contrastive model F . The reverse-time guided SDE is given by:

$$dy = [f(y, t) - g(t)^2 (s_\theta(y, t) - \nabla_y \mathcal{Q}(y, x_0, t))] dt + g(t) d\bar{w}, \quad (30)$$

where \bar{w} is the standard reverse-time Wiener process and $s_\theta(y, t)$ is the score function from the pretrained SDE. The guidance function \mathcal{Q} is defined as:

$$\mathcal{Q}(y, x, t) = -\lambda S(y, x, t) \quad (31)$$

The similarity function $S(y, x, t)$ measures how similar the generated sample x_t is to the source image y , based on hidden representations from the contrastive model F . Let $h_t = F(x_t, t)$ and $h_0 = F(y, t)$ be the features of shapes $C \times M \times N$, then:

$$S(y, x_t, t) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{h_t^{mn\top} h_0^{mn}}{|h_t^{mn}|_2, |h_0^{mn}|_2} \quad (32)$$

Here, h^{mn} represents the channel-wise feature at spatial location (m, n) . Alternatively, we can define S using negative squared $L2$ distance:

$$S(y, x_t, t) = -|h_0 - h_t|_2^2 \quad (33)$$

We compare these similarity metrics through ablation studies. Similar to Eq. (??), the update equation for the guided diffusion becomes:

$$y_{t-1} = y_t - [f(y_t, t) - g(t)^2(s_\theta(y_t, t) - \nabla_y \mathcal{Q}(y_t, x_0, t))] + g(t)z, z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I). \quad (34)$$

Algo. 2 shows the inference of pretrained SDE guided by contrastive model.

Algorithm 2 Contrastive-SDE for unpaired image-to-image translation

Require: Source image x_0 , initial time P , denoising steps R , hyper-parameter λ , similarity function $\mathcal{S}(\cdot, \cdot)$, score function $s(\cdot, \cdot)$

```

1:  $\mathbf{y} \sim q_{P|0}(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}_0)$  ▷ Start point
2:  $l \leftarrow \frac{P}{R}$ 
3: for  $i = R$  to 1 do
4:    $t \leftarrow il$ 
5:    $\mathbf{x} \sim q_{t|0}(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{x}_0)$  ▷ Sample perturbed source image
6:    $\mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t) \leftarrow -\lambda \mathcal{S}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t)$ 
7:    $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \mathbf{y} - [f(\mathbf{y}, s) - g(t)^2 s(\mathbf{y}, t) - \nabla_{\mathbf{y}} \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t)]h$ 
8:   if  $i > 1$  then
9:      $z \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, I)$ 
10:  else
11:     $z \leftarrow 0$ 
12:  end if
13:   $\mathbf{y} \leftarrow \mathbf{y} + g(t)\sqrt{l}z$ 
14: end for
15:  $\mathbf{y}_0 \leftarrow \mathbf{y}$ 
16: return  $\mathbf{y}_0$ 

```

6 Datasets

- **CelebA:** CelebA is a large-scale dataset for facial recognition, containing over 200,000 celebrity images across 10,177 identities. It is commonly used for tasks like facial recognition, attribute prediction, and generative models. The original images are 178x218 pixels. CelebA provides 40 attribute labels, such as "Smiling", "Male", "Young", "Eyeglasses", etc., for each face, making it popular for both supervised and semi-supervised learning tasks. When resized to 32x32, much of the detailed facial features and facial attribute information will be lost due to the reduction in resolution. The dataset may still be useful for tasks

like testing models on low-resolution images. It is widely used for facial recognition and generative adversarial networks (GANs), though resizing it to lower resolutions reduces the available information.

- **CIFAR-10:** CIFAR-10 is a well-known image dataset for object classification. It contains 60,000 32x32 color images in 10 different classes, with each class containing 6,000 images. The classes are: airplane, automobile, bird, cat, deer, dog, frog, horse, ship, and truck. The images are originally 32x32 pixels, and the dataset is often used for image classification tasks and for testing various neural network architectures. Resizing CIFAR-10 images is typically unnecessary since the original images are already 32x32. However, resizing them to larger or smaller sizes can be used to test the robustness of models to resolution changes. CIFAR-10 is commonly used for benchmarking models in image classification tasks, particularly with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)
- **AFHQ:** AFHQ (Animal Faces-High Quality) is a high-resolution dataset designed for image-to-image translation and generative modeling. It consists of 15,630 high-quality 512x512 color images across three domains: cats, dogs, and wildlife (e.g., foxes, tigers, lions). Each domain contains roughly 5,000 images, with diverse breeds, poses, and backgrounds. Unlike lower-resolution datasets, AFHQ’s large image size makes it suitable for testing high-fidelity synthesis and domain transfer tasks. The dataset is often used to evaluate generative adversarial networks (GANs), diffusion models, and other image translation methods. AFHQ is particularly popular for benchmarking unpaired translation methods (e.g., CycleGAN, StarGANv2) due to its clear domain separation and visual richness.

7 Experiments

7.1 Implementation

For the efficiency strategy, we trained both the baseline model and our proposed model for approximately 5×10^5 iterations. We used a batch size of 256 instead of the default 128 from the baseline, applying this setting consistently across both CelebA and CIFAR-10 datasets while keeping all other training parameters identical to the multi-stage diffusion approach. For unpaired image-to-image translation tasks, we trained the contrastive model for 5,000 iterations with a batch size of 32, learning rate of $3e-4$, and weight decay of 0.05 on AFHQ and CelebA datasets. For all unpaired translation tasks, we maintained the default settings of $\lambda = 500$ and $P = 0.5T$, though we adjusted these to $\lambda = 25$ and $P = 0.6T$ when optimizing specifically for FID improvement. All experiments are conducted on NVIDIA RTX A6000 GPU.

7.2 Evaluation metrics

For efficiency, we use metrics FID, Iterations and time taken for training the diffusion models. And for Unpaired I2I translation, we evaluate our results using two key criteria: realism and faithfulness. To measure realism, we compute the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [6] between the translated images and the target domain. For faithfulness, we quantify how well the output preserves the input’s structure using L2 distance, PSNR, and SSIM [3] between source and translated image pairs.

7.3 Results

The quantitative results of baseline model from our experiments and results reported in [27], we achieve better FID scores (improving from 1.44 to 1.16) in fewer iterations (4×10^5 vs 4.3×10^5) just by changing batch size from 128 to 256. This suggests that using iteration count alone as an efficiency metric may be misleading. Whereas our approach reduced training time by about 25%, the final FID results still fell short of expectations on both datasets. For the unpaired I2I we have achieved remarkable results using contrastive SDE. We evaluate Contrastive-SDE against several state-of-the-art (SOTA) baselines: ILVR, EGSDE (with results reproduced from publicly available code), and SDDM (results reported in [25]). The quantitative comparison in Table 1, demonstrates that Contrastive-SDE achieves near state-of-the-art performance in faithfulness metrics (L2, PSNR, SSIM), often closely matching EGSDE. For realism, as measured by FID, Contrastive-SDE does not reach the SOTA level but shows superior performance compared to ILVR in default setting. Furthermore, we demonstrate that FID can be improved by adjusting some hyperparameters, offering a flexible trade-off with other metrics. Qualitative results, illustrated in Fig. 4, showcases the quality of generated samples across all baselines. We also compare the training cost of our contrastive model with the classifier-based setup used in EGSDE on the Cat \rightarrow Dog task. As shown in Table 3, EGSDE requires approximately 7 hours of training for 5K iterations, along with labeled data to train the domain-specific classifier. In contrast, our contrastive model converges within 2K iterations in just 2 hours with no labeled data. Additionally, the average training speed is 3.6 seconds per iteration for Contrastive-SDE, compared to 5.06 seconds per iteration for EGSDE. These results show that our method not only removes the need for external classifier supervision but also offers a simpler and more efficient training pipeline.

7.4 Analysis

The Table 2 displays the time taken for both models during training for 4.0×10^5 iterations, indicating a promising 25% reduction in training time. The FID score after implementing patch diffusion for CelebA, and CIFAR10 datasets the FID 126, 240 which is not a good score for a generative model.

The poor FID performance of our patch-based multi-stage diffusion approach may be attributed to working with low-resolution 32×32 images. When these small images are divided into 8×8 patches, most patches contain insufficient meaningful information for the model to

Figure 3: FID vs Iterations

Figure 4: Qualitative comparison of Contrastive SDE with several baselines on three I2I translation tasks

Method	FID ↓	L2 ↓	PSNR ↑	SSIM ↑
Cat → Dog				
ILVR [18]	74.82 ± 0.88	57.04 ± 0.16	17.78 ± 0.02	0.360 ± 0.001
EGSDE [23]	65.88 ± 0.71	48.68 ± 0.08	19.31 ± 0.01	0.415 ± 0.001
SDDM* [25]	62.29 ± 0.63	–	–	0.422 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE	72.61 ± 0.72	48.72 ± 0.07	19.31 ± 0.01	0.425 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE [†]	61.68 ± 0.71	59.41 ± 0.10	17.54 ± 0.02	0.383 ± 0.001
Wild → Dog				
ILVR [18]	74.85 ± 0.90	63.51 ± 0.10	16.84 ± 0.02	0.304 ± 0.001
EGSDE [23]	60.13 ± 0.52	55.97 ± 0.08	18.13 ± 0.01	0.342 ± 0.001
SDDM* [25]	57.38 ± 0.53	–	–	0.328 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE	66.72 ± 0.62	56.29 ± 0.11	18.08 ± 0.01	0.345 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE [†]	59.86 ± 0.39	66.19 ± 0.15	16.64 ± 0.02	0.304 ± 0.001
Male → Female				
ILVR [18]	46.11 ± 0.44	52.10 ± 0.09	18.60 ± 0.01	0.511 ± 0.001
EGSDE [23]	42.31 ± 0.41	43.00 ± 0.03	20.35 ± 0.01	0.574 ± 0.000
SDDM* [25]	44.37 ± 0.23	–	–	0.526 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE	50.16 ± 0.18	44.18 ± 0.04	20.11 ± 0.01	0.574 ± 0.001
Contrastive-SDE [†]	45.15 ± 0.15	53.53 ± 0.06	18.44 ± 0.02	0.533 ± 0.001

Table 1: Quantitative comparison of Contrastive SDE with several baselines on three I2I translation tasks. The results marked with * came from [25]. The default setting ($\lambda = 500$, initial time $P = 0.5T$), and [†] denotes the model results with the modified setting ($\lambda = 25$, initial time $P = 0.6T$)

learn effectively. This explains why we observed reduced training time but unsatisfactory FID results. For the unpaired translation tasks, the moderate FID performance might result from using low-pass filtered versions of images during domain-invariant feature extraction. These filters may not completely eliminate domain-specific information, allowing some to persist in the hidden representations. While more sophisticated feature extractors could potentially improve results, our current faithfulness metrics confirm that the contrastive model successfully preserves domain-invariant features during the diffusion process.

Model	Dataset	p	Training Time	FID ↓
Multistage EDM	CelebA	0.5	8 days	1.16
Multistage-Patch EDM	CelebA	0.5	6 days	126
Multistage EDM	CIFAR10	0.5	7 days	2.67
Multistage-Patch EDM	CIFAR10	0.5	5 days 4 hrs	240

Table 2: Results of baseline (Multi stage Diffusion) vs (Mutistage Patch diffusion).

Method	Training time ↓	Iterations ↓	sec/iteration ↓	batch size
EGSDE	7hr	5000	5.04	32
Contrastive SDE	2hr	2000	3.6	32

Table 3: Comparison of training cost for Cat → Dog task

Figure 5: Comparison of faithfulness with initial time P

7.5 Ablation

We conduct ablation study on unpaired I2I task on parameters like initial time and score function.

Choice of Initial time P : Fig 5 illustrates an inverse relationship between P and image faithfulness: as P increases, realism improves, but faithfulness declines.

Choice of Score function \mathcal{S} : Table 4 shows the effect of score function on metrics on different λ . Regarding score functions, the NS L_2 similarity demonstrated greater sensitivity to λ . changes compared to cosine similarity, with the quantitative results clearly showing the expected trade-off between faithfulness metrics and realism metrics.

Similarity	λ	FID ↓	L2 ↓	PSNR ↑	SSIM ↑
Cosine	500	72.61	48.72	19.31	0.425
Cosine	150	72.96	49.01	19.24	0.423
NS L_2	5e-05	72.86	48.73	19.30	0.424
NS L_2	5e-03	77.80	46.42	19.75	0.428

Table 4: Results of both score functions for different λ for Cat → Dog I2I task

8 Conclusion

In this project, we worked on two major challenges in diffusion models: improving training efficiency and enhancing unpaired image-to-image translation. Our work provides practical solutions while clearly identifying current limitations that point to valuable future research directions.

For training efficiency, we developed a modified multi-stage diffusion approach that reduces training time by approximately 25% compared to standard methods while maintaining competitive image generation quality. By increasing the batch size to 256 in fewer iterations, we were able to improve fid, which concludes that iterations alone cannot be the metric for efficiency. However, our experiments revealed significant limitations when applying patch-based methods to very low-resolution images (32×32). The extreme subdivision into 8×8 patches often resulted in patches containing insufficient meaningful information, leading to poor FID performance despite the efficiency gains. This finding suggests that while our approach shows promise for efficiency improvements, the relationship between image resolution, patch size, and model performance requires further investigation.

In the domain of unpaired image-to-image translation, we introduced Contrastive-SDE, a novel framework that combines contrastive learning with stochastic differential equations. Our method demonstrates particular strength in preserving domain-invariant features during translation, achieving competitive results on key metrics including L2 distance, PSNR, and SSIM (48.72, 19.31, 0.425). Quantitative comparisons show our approach performs comparably to established methods like EGSDE in preserving important image characteristics while offering implementation advantages.

The current limitations of our approaches point clearly to needed improvements. We could explore more sophisticated domain-invariant feature extraction techniques or incorporate penalty function in loss for domain-specific features during training, using domain-specific features might increase complexity as it might another model to extract it, but using non-parameterized domain specific extractors [1, 4, 2] could eliminate the retention of domain-specific features.

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